

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part VIII. Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methoxyisocoumarin

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Starting from 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetic acid, synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methoxyisocoumarin has been effected.

TWO alternative routes, developed for the synthesis of dihydroisocoumarins, require *ortho*-nitrophenylacetates as the starting material for one¹⁻³ and appropriate homophthalates for the other⁴⁻⁶. Adopting the latter route, which has been shown to be a preferred one⁴, 3,4-dihydro-6-hydroxy-5-methoxyisocoumarin⁵ has been synthesised. But the synthesis of its isomer, 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII) by this method is precluded as the necessary homophthalate, methyl 4-benzyloxy-2-methoxyacetyl-3-methoxyphenylacetate, reported earlier⁷ in unspecified yield as a byproduct, is almost inaccessible in quantities as a starting material. Therefore the dihydroisocoumarin (VIII) was synthesised from 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetic acid (III) by the reaction sequences described previously¹. The literature method⁸ for the preparation of the nitro-acid (III) being tedious, it was conveniently obtained by the interaction of nitrous acid and 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetamide (II), prepared by the Wolff rearrangement of 4-benzyloxy- ω -diazo-3-methoxy-2-nitroacetophenone⁹ (I).

- I. R = NO₂; R₁ = COCHN₃.
 II. R = NO₂; R₁ = CH₂CONH₂.
 III. R = NO₂; R₁ = CH₂COOH.
 IV. R = NO₂; R₁ = CH₂COOMe.
 V. R = NH₂; R₁ = CH₂CH₂OH.
 VI. R = COOH; R₁ = CH₂CH₂OH.

- VII. R = CH₂Ph.
 VIII. R = H.
 IX. R = Me.

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Methyl 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetate (IV), which was next obtained by the action of diazomethane on (III), was reduced successively with lithium aluminium hydride and sodium dithionite according to the earlier procedure¹ to furnish 2-amino-4-benzyloxy-3-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (V), isolated as its hydrochloride. After diazotisation, it was converted into the nitrile which was hydrolysed without purification by sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution, on acidification, did not provide the expected dihydroisocoumarin (VII), but afforded 4-benzyloxy-2-carboxy-3-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (VI). It is readily soluble in aqueous bicarbonate, reprecipitated on acidification and crystallises from ethyl acetate-light petroleum in fine needles, m.p. 140°. In contrast to the instability of some dimethoxy 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohols¹⁻³, the isolation of the stable hydroxy-acid (VI), like its isomer 4-benzyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol,¹⁰ lends support to our previous observation that the ease with which 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohols form δ -lactones is dependent on the nature and position of the substituents in the benzene ring¹⁰.

Lactonisation of (VI) by sublimation *in vacuo*, however, afforded, 7-benzyloxy-3,4-dihydro-8-methoxyisocoumarin (VII) which was debenzylated by catalytic hydrogenation over palladised charcoal to furnish 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII), methylation of which with diazomethane provided 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IX), identical with the authentic specimen prepared earlier¹.

*EXPERIMENTAL

4-Benzyl-oxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetamide (II).—4-Benzyl-oxy- ω -diazo-3-methoxy-2-nitroacetophenone⁹ (I) (5 g.) in dioxane (65 ml) at 40° was treated with ammonia (40 ml, *d* 0.88) and aqueous silver nitrate (10 ml, 10%); the temperature was then raised to 50°. After 1½ hrs., ammonia (10 ml, *d* 0.88) and aqueous silver nitrate (5 ml, 10%) were again added and the temperature was raised to and maintained at 55° for 1 hour, at 60° for another hour, and at 70° for ½ hr. Finally, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 mins. with the addition of a little charcoal and filtered. The cooled filtrate, on dilution with water to turbidity, gradually deposited a brown solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate to yield the amide (II) as pale yellow prismatic needles (3.4 g., 71%), m.p. 133-34°. Recrystallisation from aqueous dioxane furnished the analytical specimen as colorless needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 4.9. C₁₆H₁₆O₅N₂ requires C, 60.75; H, 5.06%).

4-Benzyl-oxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetic Acid (III).—Powdered sodium nitrite (4.5 g.) was added in small portions during 1 hour to a stirred solution of the amide (II) (7 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and H₂SO₄ (75 ml, 50% v/v) at 25-30°. Vigorous frothing developed during the reaction was controlled by adding a little acetic acid at frequent intervals. Stirring was continued for another hour. Water (150 ml) was added to the reaction mixture which was later cooled in a bath of freezing mixture. The white precipitate formed was purified by dissolving in aqueous sodium carbonate and reprecipitating with acid. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol to furnish the acid (III) as colorless needles (6g., 85%), m.p. 144° (lit.⁸ m.p. 144°).

10. Sinha and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 437.

*All m.p.s. uncorrected. Petroleum used had b. p. 60-80° unless otherwise stated. The extracts with organic solvents were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate.

Methyl 4-Benzoyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetate (IV).—To a cooled solution of the preceding acid (III) (10 g.) in methanol (30 ml) excess ethereal diazomethane, prepared from *N*-nitrosomethylurea (10 g.), was slowly added and the mixture kept overnight at room temperature. Unchanged diazomethane was removed by addition of a small amount of acetic acid; the ether solution was successively washed with water, dilute sodium carbonate, and water and dried. Evaporation of the ether furnished the acetate (IV) as an oil which soon solidified to a mass of yellow needles (9.6 g., 96%), m. p. 47–48°. Recrystallisation from dilute methanol (ice-chest) afforded the pure specimen as colorless needles, m. p. 53–54°. (Found: C, 61.3; H, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6N$ requires C, 61.6; H, 5.1%.)

2-Amino-4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (V).—A solution of the ester (IV) (3.31 g.) in dry ether (50 ml) was added dropwise to a well-stirred suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (0.7 g.) in dry ether (50 ml), cooled to -10° , and the stirring continued for 1 hour at that temperature. After allowing it to stand overnight at room temperature, the excess hydride and the complex were decomposed by addition of a saturated solution of sodium sulphate, followed by $2N-H_2SO_4$; the ether layer was separated and the aqueous acidic layer extracted with ethyl acetate (8 × 25 ml). The two extracts were combined, washed with water, dried, and the solvents distilled. The deep red gummy residue was dissolved in hot ethanol (125 ml); water (50 ml) and sodium dithionite (8 g.) were added and the mixture was gently refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. During this period, water (75 ml) was added in instalments to dissolve the dithionite; gradually the red colour of the solution was discharged. After distilling most of the ethanol, the solution was extracted with chloroform (2 × 50 ml.), the extract was dried, and the solvent evaporated. The oily residue was taken up in cold ether and treated with a chilled and saturated solution of dry HCl in ether when a grey solid was obtained. Sublimation in *vacuo* (bath temp. $160-70^\circ/0.2$ mm) afforded the hydrochloride of (V) as colorless needles (1.8 g., 60%), m. p. 170° (darkening). (Found: C, 61.9; H, 6.0. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3NCl$ requires C, 62.0; H, 6.4%.)

4-Benzoyloxy-2-carboxy-3-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (VI).—A suspension of the preceding compound (2.2 g.) in HCl (2.6 ml, *d* 1.16) and water (50 ml) was diazotised at $0-5^\circ$ with sodium nitrite (0.8 g.) in water (7 ml). After neutralisation with anhydrous sodium carbonate, the diazonium solution was added to a solution of potassium cyanide (3 g.), nickel chloride (2 g.), and anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.7 g.) in water (60 ml.) at 10° with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was cooled and extracted with chloroform (3 × 25 ml); the extract was dried and the solvent evaporated to provide a gum. The gum was refluxed with a solution of KOH (5 g.) in aqueous-ethanol (1:1; 50 ml) for 20 hours, most of the ethanol distilled, cooled, and acidified with HCl (conc.) (Congo red). The brown solid separating was dissolved in aqueous bicarbonate, filtered, and the filtrate acidified to reprecipitate the acid (VI). It was crystallised twice from ethyl acetate-petroleum as colorless needles (1.2 g., 60%), m. p. $139-40^\circ$. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 5.9%.)

7-Benzoyloxy-3,4-dihydro-8-methoxyisocoumarin (VII).—The preceding compound (VI) (500 mg.) was heated under reduced pressure (bath temp. $135-40^\circ/0.2$ mm) using a cold finger when a colorless crystalline sublimate of (VII) (400 mg., 85%) was deposited. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum as colorless prisms, m. p. 87° . (Found: C, 71.7; H, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%.)

3,4-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-8-methoxycoumarin (VIII).—A solution of the above dihydroisocoumarin (VII) (300 mg.) in pure methanol (30 ml) was hydrogenated over palladised charcoal¹¹ (30 mg., 10%) at room temperature and pressure until the absorption of hydrogen had ceased. The solution was filtered and evaporated to a white solid. On crystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum (ice chest) (VIII) was obtained as colorless needles (195 mg., 95%), m.p. 134-35° with previous sintering at 132°. It gave an intense yellow colour with a faint greenish tinge with aqueous ethanolic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 61.85; H, 5.15%).

A solution of the above compound (VIII) (100 mg.) in methanol (10 ml) was treated at 0° with ethereal diazomethane, prepared from *N*-nitrosomethylurea (1 g.), and left overnight at room temperature. Evaporation of the solvent left a colorless gum which soon solidified. It was sublimed in *vacuo* (bath temp. 115-20°/0.2 mm.) and the sublimate crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) with a trace of chloroform to furnish 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (IX) as colorless rectangular prisms (90 mg., 93%), m.p. 92°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared earlier¹ by a different method.

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